

MICE TOURISM AS A DRIVER OF TOURIST AND EXCURSION SERVICES DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF CONTEMPORARY GLOBAL TRENDS

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Abstract. *This paper examines the current state and future prospects of MICE tourism as a strategic direction for developing tourist and excursion services in Uzbekistan. Statistical data, legislative acts, and investment projects are analyzed to identify key trends and factors influencing the sector's growth. The study reviews the main segments of MICE tourism and related infrastructure, provides examples of implemented projects and development plans, and pays special attention to the role of public-private partnerships, international cooperation, and digitalization in advancing the MICE industry. The conclusion highlights Uzbekistan's potential to become a MICE tourism hub in Central Asia and presents recommendations for further development.*

Keywords: *MICE tourism, Uzbekistan, business tourism, meetings, incentive tours, excursions, conferences, exhibitions, infrastructure, investment, public-private partnership, digitalization, Central Asia, tourism.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda turistik-ekskursion xizmatlarni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida MICE-turizmning hozirgi holati va istiqbollari ko'rib chiqiladi. Sektor rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan asosiy tendensiyalar va omillarni aniqlash maqsadida statistik ma'lumotlar, normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar hamda investitsiyaviy loyihalar tahlil qilinadi. MICE-turizmning asosiy segmentlari, infratuzilmasi, amaliy misollar va kelajak rejalari muhokama etiladi. Davlat-xususiy sherikchiligi, xalqaro hamkorlik va raqamlashtirishning MICE-industriya rivojlanishidagi o'rni alohida e'tiborga olinadi. Xulosa o'rnida O'zbekistonning Markaziy Osiyoda MICE-turizm markazi sifatidagi salohiyati yoritilib, sohani yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ilgari suriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *MICE-turizm, O'zbekiston, biznes-turizm, uchrashuvlar, incentiv-turlar, ekskursioniyalar, konferensiyalar, ko'rgazmalar, infratuzilma, investitsiyalar, davlat-xususiy sherikchilik, raqamlashtirish, Markaziy Osiyo, turizm.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается текущее состояние и перспективы MICE-туризма, как одного из направлений развития туристско-экскурсионных услуг в Узбекистане. Проводится анализ статистических данных, законодательных актов, инвестиционных проектов для выявления ключевых тенденций и факторов, влияющих на развитие сектора. Рассматриваются основные сегменты MICE-туризма, инфраструктура, приводятся примеры и планы на будущее. Особое внимание уделяется роли государственно-частного партнерства, международному сотрудничеству и цифровизации в контексте развития MICE-индустрии. В заключении формулируются выводы о потенциале Узбекистана как центра MICE-туризма в Центральной Азии и предлагаются рекомендации по дальнейшему развитию.*

Ключевые слова: MICE-туризм, Узбекистан, деловой туризм, встречи, инсентив-туры, экскурсии, конференции, выставки, инфраструктура, инвестиции, государственно-частное партнерство, цифровизация, Центральная Азия, туризм.

Introduction

MICE tourism, as one of the most dynamically developing segments of the tourism industry, plays a crucial role in the economic growth of countries and regions. It facilitates attracting investments, creating new jobs, improving infrastructure, enhancing a country's image on the international stage, and promoting intercultural exchange. MICE tourism encompasses the organization and conduct of corporate meetings, incentive trips, conferences, and exhibitions (Cheglazova & Zalesova 2020: p. 417). In today's context, the MICE sector is inextricably linked to global trends in tourism, including the rise of hybrid event formats, accelerated digitalization, and the increasing appeal of excursion programs as part of business trips.

Uzbekistan, situated along the historic Silk Road, boasts a rich cultural and historical heritage, unique natural landscapes, and a developing economy. In recent years, the country has actively implemented reforms aimed at liberalizing the economy, creating a favorable investment climate, and expanding the tourism sector. Notably, under the “Travel in Uzbekistan” program, included in the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022 – 2026 (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2022a), the goal is to increase the number of domestic tourists to 12 million and international tourists to 9 million by 2026, doubling employment in the tourism sector to 520,000, and implementing tourism projects totaling US\$300 million, generating 25,000 new jobs.

Pursuant to the Presidential Decree of 9 February 2021, No. UP-6165, a practice of reimbursing part of travel expenses and launching new air routes as well as increasing the number of railway connections have been introduced to foster domestic and pilgrimage tourism (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2021). According to the Decree of 13 August 2019, No. UP-5781, from 1 January 2020, a 30-day visa-free regime has been established for citizens of several countries, stimulating inbound tourism (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2019a). Furthermore, the Decree of 5 January 2019, No. UP-5611, approved the Tourism Development Concept in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019 – 2025, which provides for measures to liberalize the visa regime and improve tourism infrastructure (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2019b).

These and many other measures create favorable conditions for the successful development of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan. A key aspect here is integrating business events with excursion programs, reflecting global best practices that combine professional objectives with cultural and exploratory purposes. The aim of this article is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the current state of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan, identify the main trends and future prospects, and determine the crucial enabling and inhibiting factors shaping the sector's growth.

Methods

This research is based on an analysis of a broad range of information sources, including:

- Statistical data: Information from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, and international organizations (ICCA, UNWTO, etc.).

- Regulatory documents: presidential decrees and resolutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with laws and subordinate regulations governing tourism and investment activities.

- Reports and analytical materials: publications by consulting firms, research centers, international organizations, and industry associations.

- Media materials: articles and news in print and electronic outlets covering tourism development in Uzbekistan.

- Specialized websites: open-source materials from travel agencies, event organizers, convention centers, and exhibition complexes.

Quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods are utilized. The quantitative analysis includes processing of statistical data and constructing tables and graphs to visualize trends. Qualitative analysis involves studying regulatory acts, expert opinions, and relevant projects to identify factors influencing the development of MICE tourism.

Results

1. General Overview of the Tourism Sector in Uzbekistan

The government identifies tourism as a strategic priority for economic development. Consequently, Uzbekistan’s tourism industry has shown a steady expansion in recent years, reflected in continuous growth in international arrivals and an increase in tourism export earnings (Table 1).

Table 1
Dynamics of Inbound Tourism in Uzbekistan (2017 – 2024)

Year	Number of Tourists (million people)	Export of Tourism Services (USD billion)	Source
2017	2.69	1.55	(Embassy of Uzbekistan in Turkey 2023)
2018	5.3	1.041	(Uzbekistan Travel 2023)
2019	6.748	1.313	(Uzbekistan Travel 2023)
2020	1.5	0.261	(State Committee... 2020; Economic Review 2023)
2021	1.88	0.296	(Embassy of Uzbekistan in Turkey 2023)
2022	5.2	1.61	(Embassy of Uzbekistan in Turkey 2023)
2023	6.6	2.1435	(Uzbekistan.org 2024)
2024	10.2	3.5	(UzDaily 2025; Profi.Travel 2025)
2025	12 (forecast)	3.8 (forecast)	(UzDaily 2025)

Although the COVID-19 pandemic led to a sharp drop in tourist arrivals in 2020, the actual data up to 2024 and projections for 2025 confirm a positive growth trend of inbound tourism and tourism export revenues in Uzbekistan (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Growth of inbound tourism and export of tourism services in Uzbekistan, 2017 – 2025

2. Review of MICE Infrastructure in Uzbekistan’s Cities

The development of MICE tourism requires modern infrastructure, including:

- Convention centers, exhibition complexes, and venues for large-scale conferences, forums, trade fairs, and other business events.
- Hotels capable of accommodating event participants, ranging from budget to premium-class properties.
- Transportation infrastructure – airports, railway stations, roads, public transport, ensuring convenient mobility for participants.
- Support infrastructure – restaurants, cafes, cultural and entertainment facilities, interpreting services, ICT resources, event technology, etc.

Uzbekistan is actively working to improve each of these components. Major cities are demonstrating progress as follows:

Tashkent

As the country’s capital, Tashkent is the principal center of business activity and MICE tourism. In addition to existing facilities, the large-scale *Tashkent City* project is being developed, which includes:

- A modern Congress Hall equipped to host events of various scales, featuring 16 meeting rooms with a combined capacity of up to 5,000 participants.
- The five-star Hilton Tashkent City Hotel, offering 250 rooms and five conference halls with a total capacity of up to 1,500 people (Fatkalislamova 2021).
- Grade-A office towers in newly built business centers.
- Leisure and networking spaces in shopping and entertainment centers.

Samarkand

Samarkand, one of the world’s oldest cities and a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is also pursuing active MICE infrastructure development.

Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 828 of 30 September 2019 (2019d) emphasizes MICE tourism in the Samarkand region through the following initiatives:

- Hosting international events: Annual planning of at least one international forum, conference, seminar, roundtable, etc., in Samarkand region, considering the unified calendar of cultural, entertainment, and mass sporting events.

- Utilizing existing infrastructure: Compiling an inventory of current facilities capable of hosting MICE events and developing measures to encourage their active use.

These measures aim to strengthen Samarkand’s position as an attractive destination for business tourism, encouraging more international events and the development of corresponding infrastructure.

Bolstered by direct investments, the Silk Road Samarkand tourism complex was constructed in 2023 (Silk Road Samarkand 2023), comprising:

- A multifunctional congress center with a capacity of 3,500 seats, designed for international conferences, forums, exhibitions, and other events.

- Eight international-brand hotels, including Hilton, with approximately 1,200 rooms in total.

Bukhara

Bukhara, another historic city in Uzbekistan, also has great potential for MICE tourism. According to presidential resolutions, a series of initiatives was implemented between 2019 and 2023 to develop the city and region (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2019c). These initiatives included investments in tourism infrastructure, the construction of new high-end hotels such as Wyndham Bukhara 5*, Grand Ark Bukhara 5*, Reikartz Bahor, and Mercure Bukhara Old Town, along with creating contemporary conference rooms and other facilities required for hosting business events.

Alongside targeted investments in tourism infrastructure, measures to develop industry, agribusiness, and transport logistics have been pivotal in strengthening Bukhara’s standing as a MICE hub. Improvements to transport infrastructure include new permits for foreign airlines to operate direct flights from Southeast Asian cities to Bukhara, increased frequency of road and rail connections with other major Uzbek cities, thereby enhancing the region’s accessibility for business gatherings. Improvements in the business climate, the attraction of foreign investments, and the establishment of modern business spaces have increased the number of international events, spurring growth in demand for hotel accommodations, public catering (including halal standards), and other tourist services (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2019c).

This integrated approach, encompassing economic reforms, urban modernization, and support for entrepreneurship, not only attracted new business ventures but also unlocked additional opportunities for boosting tourism, cementing Bukhara’s status as a leading destination for both business and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan.

Bukhara’s example illustrates that other historical centers – Khiva, Shakhrisabz, Kokand, Andijan, Margilan, and Fergana – also possess rich cultural legacies that can be leveraged to host MICE events, particularly when combined with cultural and historical tours (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2022b). However, developing MICE infrastructure in these cities will require further investments and efforts.

3. Analysis of MICE Segments

Despite rising interest in MICE tourism in Uzbekistan, publicly available statistical data on MICE segments remain limited. The present discussion draws on fragmentary data, providing an overview of trends and prospects rather than a detailed quantitative assessment.

Meetings

The meetings segment dominates Uzbekistan’s MICE market, accounting for up to 90% of the sector. On average, the country hosts about 9.3 corporate events per month, each lasting approximately 1.8 days or longer, with an average of 53 participants (Farhodova & Mulladjanova 2024: p. 112).

Business ties with international partners are actively growing. For instance, during ICTWEEK 2024, IT Park held over 40 meetings with leading global companies, resulting in 14 companies registering legal entities in Uzbekistan and another 13 in the process of doing so (IT Park Uzbekistan 2024).

Incentives

On the global level, incentive tours account for a notable share – up to 9.3% of the MICE market (Kireeva 2022: p. 19), with an annual growth forecast of 3.4% (Novikov 2024: p. 3). In Uzbekistan, some studies estimate that recreational events make up 10 – 20% of the overall MICE market (Farhodova & Mulladjanova 2024: p. 112), although no detailed statistics are available on the dynamics of this segment.

It is important to note that “eastern hospitality” in Uzbekistan is not merely a tradition but rather a “philosophy of life.” The incentive format frequently complements business meetings, conferences, and exhibitions. While company-organized incentive trips, workshops, and trainings to build team spirit and employee development are relatively new, arranging recreational activities to strengthen business ties with partners and clients is deeply embedded in local culture.

Incentive programs include festive pilaf in national teahouses, folk ensemble performances, visits to ancient cities, artisans’ workshops, pilgrimage visits to holy sites, eco-tours to nature reserves, mountains, and deserts, and visits to mausoleums and sacred places. A distinct feature of incentives in Uzbekistan is the exclusive, customized format – designing one-of-a-kind routes and programs aligned with a company’s goals, combining leisure and activity.

Conferences

Conferences typically involve representatives of government agencies, international organizations, universities, research centers, entrepreneurs, investors, analysts, and journalists, focusing on areas such as economics, investment (Samarkand International Tourism Forum, Tashkent International Investment Forum, Uzbekistan Economic Forum), science and education (annual international conferences of leading universities), climate and the environment (Central Asia Climate Change Conference), and more. Specialized conferences on MICE tourism also take place, such as the 2022 scientific-practical conference in Kokand (UzDaily 2022).

Many events are conducted in English, Russian, and Uzbek, ensuring convenience for diverse participants. Partners for large-scale forums include international organizations (World Bank, UN, EBRD, UNWTO). At the regional level, the comprehensive “Meetings & Events Catalogue” was released to streamline and stimulate the MICE industry, serving as a specialized reference guide (Muminov 2022: p. 5).

Exhibitions

Exhibitions primarily aim to showcase products, sign commercial contracts, attract investments, and find distributors and partners. In Uzbekistan, annual exhibitions cover:

- Industry and technology – UzBuild, UzTechExpo, ICTWEEK Uzbekistan.
- Agriculture – AgroExpo Uzbekistan.
- Tourism and culture – Silk Road Tourism Fair.

4. State Support and Investment

The Uzbek government actively supports MICE tourism as a priority for economic diversification. Each year, investment in international tourism increases. Regulatory acts are enacted to encourage tourism growth, create a favorable investment climate, and simplify visa procedures. Tax incentives and other benefits are provided to investors implementing projects in tourism. Public-private partnerships in the sector are thriving, facilitating private investment in developing and managing tourism infrastructure. Infrastructure improvements continue at pace.

Presidential Decree No. UP-102 of 18 July 2024 established measures to upgrade tourism infrastructure and increase foreign tourist arrivals. The document aims to enhance the business environment in tourism and expand the export of tourism services. Specifically, from 1 January 2025, regional budgets are recommended to allocate funds for participating in international fairs and exhibitions; meanwhile, beginning 1 September 2024, the Fund for Reconstruction and Development will extend a credit line of US\$50 million through commercial banks to provide working capital for inbound tour operators. Loans are available for 10 years at 14% annual interest with a 2-year grace period, and banks add a margin of up to 3%. Until 1 August 2025, tour operators registered in the Republic of Karakalpakstan can pay only 25% of the prevailing rate of customs duties and recycling fees on imported vehicles for organizing extreme tours, with payment deferred over three years. Additionally, until 1 August 2025, tourism-related businesses are exempt from customs duties on the import of new Euro-5 or higher standard buses and minibuses (Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2024).

5. International Cooperation

Uzbekistan is actively developing international collaborations in tourism, including MICE. The country is a member of the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and other relevant global institutions, and has established cooperation with the International Congress and Convention Association (ICCA) (InterForum 2024). Uzbekistan also maintains tourism cooperation agreements with Russia, Kazakhstan, the Republic of Korea, the UAE, and other countries, thereby boosting tourist flow and attracting investments (Official Website of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2024; Azizova et al. 2023: p. 405).

6. Digitalization

Digitalization also plays a key role in the development of MICE tourism, providing new opportunities for both organizers and participants:

- Online registration and ticket sales, streamlining registration and ticket purchases for events.
- Virtual and hybrid events, hosted entirely online or via a combined online/offline format, expanding reach and reducing costs.
- Mobile applications for event participants, offering information on schedules, speakers, venues, etc.
- Online platforms facilitating digital networking, appointment scheduling, and virtual business meetings.
- Big Data and analytics, used to gather and analyze data about MICE events, enhancing organizational efficiency.

7. Human Capital

Uzbekistan is working to train specialists equipped with modern competencies in MICE tourism (Atoeva 2023: p. 159):

- Higher education and colleges are introducing specializations in event management, hospitality, and tourism.

- Professional development programs and master classes, hosted by international experts, aim to raise the qualifications of specialists.
- Institutional partnerships with foreign universities and training centers promote knowledge exchange and workforce development.

8. SWOT Analysis of MICE Tourism in Uzbekistan

A SWOT analysis provides a comprehensive view of the current status and prospects of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan, clarifying the country’s existing internal resources and advantages (e.g., governmental support, the expansion of international hotel chains), as well as gaps that need addressing (infrastructure, workforce, technology). Simultaneously, it pinpoints external opportunities and threats – such as competition from other regions and global economic conditions – that could influence successful strategy implementation.

Table 2

SWOT Analysis of MICE Tourism in Uzbekistan

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich cultural and historical heritage. • Growing interest in Uzbekistan as a tourism destination. • Government support for tourism, including the MICE sector. • Relatively low cost of hosting events compared to other countries. • Improved transport accessibility (new flights, airport modernization). • Expanding hotel infrastructure, including international chains. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficiently developed MICE infrastructure, particularly outside Tashkent, Bukhara, and Samarkand. • Shortage of qualified professionals specializing in MICE event management. • Inadequate international promotion of Uzbekistan as a MICE destination. • Limited use of digital technologies in organizing MICE events. • Some seasonality constraints (although less pronounced than in leisure tourism).
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attracting major international events (conferences, exhibitions, forums). • Strengthening cooperation with global organizations (ICCA, UNWTO). • Developing public-private partnerships to attract investments in MICE infrastructure. • Leveraging digital technologies to promote and organize MICE events. • Offering combined tours (MICE + cultural/historical tourism). • Growing domestic MICE tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competition from neighboring Central Asian countries and other regions. • Natural or force majeure events that affect the tourism industry. • Insufficient funding of MICE tourism development programs. • Non-compliance with international service standards.

Discussion

The analysis of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan indicates a substantial growth potential. The country enjoys several competitive advantages: a rich cultural heritage, increasing international interest, strong governmental support, and relatively affordable costs for event hosting.

However, full realization of this potential necessitates overcoming certain challenges. Foremost among these is the expansion of MICE infrastructure, especially in regions beyond Tashkent, Bukhara, and Samarkand. Further improvements are needed in transport and logistics, as well as the construction of modern exhibition and convention facilities and internationally standardized hotels.

Another pivotal factor is workforce development. Uzbekistan needs to continue implementing educational programs aligned with international standards, conducting training sessions and master classes with global experts, and fostering partnerships with international academic institutions.

Promoting Uzbekistan as a MICE destination on the global stage is also vital. Enhanced participation in international tourism exhibitions and forums, cooperation with organizations like ICCA, and leveraging digital technologies will help attract event organizers.

Digitalizing the MICE industry opens new opportunities to improve event organization and delivery, participant engagement, and service quality. Online registration, virtual and hybrid formats, mobile apps, and data analytics are essential elements of a modern MICE ecosystem.

Public-private partnerships play a significant role in drawing investment to develop MICE infrastructure. Offering favorable conditions to investors, such as tax incentives and simplified administrative processes, will facilitate new projects in this domain.

Lastly, integrating business activities with cultural tours allows visitors to explore Uzbekistan’s historical and cultural treasures, resonating with the global “bleisure” (business + leisure) trend and offering a powerful incentive for inbound tourism.

Recommendations

Based on the conducted analysis, the following recommendations can be formulated for the development of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan:

- **Development of MICE Infrastructure** through the construction of modern congress centers and exhibition complexes in various regions of Uzbekistan, not only in Tashkent and Samarkand. Attracting investments for the construction of hotels of different categories that meet international standards. Modernizing transport infrastructure (airports, railway stations, roads). Developing supporting infrastructure (restaurants, cafes, cultural and entertainment facilities).

- **Workforce Training** through the implementation of educational programs for MICE tourism specialists in universities and colleges. Organizing training sessions and master classes with the participation of international experts. Cooperating with international educational institutions. Enhancing foreign language proficiency among tourism industry employees.

- **Promotion of Uzbekistan as a MICE Destination** through active participation in international tourism exhibitions and forums. Collaborating with international organizations (ICCA, UNWTO). Utilizing digital technologies for promotion (social media, online platforms, targeted advertising). Developing and implementing a marketing strategy aimed at attracting MICE event organizers. Creating a specialized website dedicated to MICE tourism in Uzbekistan.

- **Digitalization**, which includes the introduction of online registration and ticket sales for events, the development of virtual and hybrid event formats, the creation of mobile applications for event participants, the use of online platforms for participant interaction, and the

application of Big Data and analytics technologies to enhance the efficiency of event organization.

- **Public-Private Partnership**, which involves creating favorable conditions for investors implementing projects in the MICE tourism sector, providing tax incentives and preferences, simplifying administrative procedures, and developing and implementing joint projects involving both the state and private businesses.

- **Development of Domestic MICE Tourism** by encouraging corporate events, conferences, and exhibitions within the country and designing special programs and offers for Uzbek companies.

- **Implementation of Sustainability Principles in the MICE Industry**, including minimizing environmental impact, supporting local communities, and preserving cultural heritage.

- **Active Inclusion of Excursion Components in Business Tours**, which will allow MICE guests to discover Uzbekistan’s unique sites and increase demand for local tourism and excursion services.

Conclusion

Thus, MICE tourism in Uzbekistan has significant growth potential and serves as a driver for the development of tourism and excursion services. Thanks to its rich cultural and historical heritage, growing international interest, government support, and developing infrastructure, Uzbekistan has every opportunity to become one of the leading MICE tourism centers in Central Asia. Moreover, global trends (hybrid formats, digitalization) create new opportunities for integrating business trips with excursion programs, making the country even more attractive for inbound tourists. The implementation of the proposed recommendations will strengthen Uzbekistan’s position in the global MICE industry market, attract investments, create new jobs, and contribute to the overall economic development of the country.

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